

Enantioselective synthesis of a functionalized 3-methylenetetrahydropyran building block for possible conversion to neoliacinic acid[†]

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A convergent approach to **5** that involves the coupling of **11** to **17** has been devised in anticipation of the ultimate elaboration of neoliacinic acid (**1**).

Neoliacinic acid (**1**) was first isolated in 1987 along with neoliacine (**2**) from the leaves of *Neolitsea acciculata* Koidz by Takaoka and coworkers¹. These architecturally attractive metabolites belong to the *Lauraceae* family, which includes various structurally related compounds¹⁻³. Neoliacine shows moderate *in vitro* cytotoxicity against Hela cell cultures, and similar antitumor activity is expected of **1**¹. Extraction of ten kilograms of fresh leaves with acetone and subsequent methylation of the acidic portion of the extracts with diazomethane furnished methyl neoliacinate (**3**). The identity of **3** was ultimately established by single crystal X-ray analysis, which unambiguously revealed the presence of six stereogenic centers, five of which are contiguous along the contour of a substantially oxygenated 6-5-8 ring system.

Two approaches to **1** have earlier been documented. The first route, due to Clark and coworkers⁴, approached construction of the two larger rings by imaginative utilization of two metal carbenoid intermediates to install the relative stereochemistry of the 6-8 ring system in an expeditious manner. In contrast, Kort sought to employ an Ireland-Claisen rearrangement of an allenylsilane for installing the six-membered ring⁵. However, neither this protocol nor an alternative radical cyclization pathway were successful.

Our synthetic plan has centered about the possibility of

constructing **4** by chemoselective oxygenation of **5**, which was to be obtained in turn by proper cyclization of vinyl oxirane **6** (Scheme 1). The present report details a convergent approach to **6** and its uneventful conversion into **5**.

Scheme 1

This undertaking began by evaluating the possibility that aldehyde **7**, previously prepared by Coulton and Southgate⁶, could serve as a useful precursor of iodide **11**. Its treatment with lithium trimethylsilylacetylide and subsequent oxidation with pyridinium dichromate gave alkyne **8** in high yield (Scheme 2). Of the several possibilities for enantioselective reduction of **8** to **9**, Noyori's binaphthol-LAH complex⁷ proved most workable on a 30-gram scale (90% of **9**), although it was less than ideal from the asymmetric induction perspective (61% ee). Since the subsequent conversion of **9** into **11** proceeded without complication, we next sought to intersect this scheme at **10** in a more expeditious way.

To this end, trimethylsilylacetylene was formylated according to Klumpp⁸ to generate **12**, the alkylation of which

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with (-)-*B*-allyl(diisopinocampheyl)borane⁹ furnished propargylic alcohol **13** with somewhat improved levels of enantioselection (72% ee) (Scheme 3). After *O*-silylation, the double bond was selectively ozonized over the triple

Scheme 2

bond¹⁰. If the progress of this transformation was monitored by TLC in advance of reductive workup, carbinol **10** was again isolated. The major advantages to the latter reaction sequence other than somewhat improved enantioselectivity are the greater ease of isolation of the intermediates and increased overall efficiency.

Scheme 3

With these results in hand, the time had come to construct epoxy aldehyde **17**. This goal was reached by condensing *cis*-butene-1,4-diol with *p*-anisaldehyde and subsequent reduction of the seven-membered acetal with Dibal-H to deliver **15**¹¹. Sharpless epoxidation of **15** proved to be problematic^{11,12} in that **16** was formed with only moderate optical purity (56% ee) (Scheme 4). Swern oxidation¹³ of

16 gave the targeted **17** and set the stage for coupling to **11**. This reaction was assumed to proceed in a non-chelation controlled manner to provide **18**. In actuality, a single carbinol was isolated in 72% yield. Ensuing oxidation of **18** with the Dess-Martin periodinane reagent¹⁴ furnished **19**, the Wittig olefination of which with methylenetriphenylphosphorane proceeded unexpectedly in low yield to give **20**.

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Scheme 4

This vinyl epoxide was recognized to offer the option of two six-membered cyclization pathways. While the desired direct S_N2 displacement is activated by virtue of the allylic character of the oxiranyl C–O bond, this advantage also ap-

plies to the S_N alternative¹⁵. The potential competitiveness of the unwanted alternative was manifested when **20** was treated with TBAF in THF at room temperature. Under these conditions, a mixture of **6** and the pyran **21** resulted. Fortunately, when the same reaction was performed at -15° , the major product isolated in 68% yield was **6**.

The cyclization of **6** was met with an entirely similar pattern of reactivity. On exposure to CSA in CH_2Cl_2 at 20° , a mixture of **5** (46%) and **21** (15%) was produced. However, cooling of the reaction mixture to -15° provided an increased amount (74%) of **5** alongside a trace quantity of **21**.

The 3-methylenetetrahydropyran **5** that forms the central ring of neoliacinic acid can therefore be conveniently assembled from the pair of chiral precursors **11** and **17**. This intermediate gives every indication of being adequately functionalized, particularly in connection with the location and inherent chemical diversity of the three ring substituents, to allow suitable advancement toward **1**.

Experimental

1-(Trimethylsilyl)-5-(triphenylmethoxy)pent-1-yn-3-one (8): Trimethylsilylacetylene (1.15 ml, 7.31 mmol) was placed in THF (30 ml) and cooled to -78° whereupon *n*-butyllithium (3.35 ml, 1.6 M in hexane, 5.4 mmol) was added dropwise. The mixture was stirred for 15 min whereupon **7** (1.13 g, 3.57 mmol) in THF (10 ml) was transferred via cannula and washed in with THF (10 ml). Reaction was complete within a minute (by TLC) and the mixture was concentrated and flash chromatographed on silica gel (25% ether/hexane) to give carbinol as a clear oil (1.26 g, 85%) (Found : C, 78.06; H, 7.42. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{Si}$ calcd. for : C, 78.22; H, 7.29%); ν_{max} (film) 3440, 1100 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.55 (6H, d, J 7.1 Hz), 7.14 (9H, m), 4.64 (1H, dd, J 5.7, 12.7 Hz), 3.44 (1H, m), 3.33 (1H, m), 2.78 (1H, d, J 7.1 Hz), 1.98 (2H, m), 1.98 (2H, m), 0.19 (9H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 143.8, 128.6, 127.9, 127.0, 106.1, 89.3, 87.2, 61.6, 61.0, 37.4, -0.1 ; m/z (M^+) calcd. 414.2015, obsd. 414.2015.

A solution of this alcohol (403 mg, 0.97 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (50 ml) was treated with 4 Å molecular sieves (0.43 g), stirred for 15 min, admixed with pyridinium dichromate (0.77 g, 2.0 mmol) in one portion, stirred for 3 h, filtered through alumina (type II, neutral), and concentrated to give **8** as a slightly yellow amorphous solid (0.377 g, 94%), m.p. 99.6 – 101.8° (Found : C, 78.39; H, 7.26. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_2\text{Si}$ calcd. for : C, 78.59; H, 6.84%); ν_{max} (film) 1675, 1075 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.46 (6H, m), 7.15 (9H, m), 3.48 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz), 2.82 (2H, t, J 6.3 Hz), 0.23 (9H, s);

^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 185.8, 143.8, 128.6, 127.8, 127.0, 101.9, 98.3, 86.8, 59.0, 45.8, -0.8 ; m/z (M^+) calcd. 412.1850, obsd. 412.1854.

(3R)-1-(Trimethylsilyl)-5-(triphenylmethoxy)pent-1-yn-3-ol (9): To LiAlH_4 (43.4 ml, 1.0 M in THF, 43.4 mmol) at rt was added MeOH (21.7 ml, 2.0 M in THF, 43.4 mmol) dropwise. After 15 min, (*R*)-(+)-binaphthol in THF (100 ml) was added via cannula to the above mixture, which was cooled to -78° after 30 min. A solution of **8** (7.16 g, 17.4 mmol) dissolved in THF (50 ml) was added slowly to the above cooled mixture during 30 min. After 1 h, the reaction mixture was treated with MeOH (7 ml) prior to being poured into 1 N HCl (50 ml), extracted with ether (6×15 ml), dried over K_2CO_3 , concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel (20% ether/hexane) to give **9** as a clear oil (5.74 g, 80%) (Found : C, 78.06; H, 7.42. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{Si}$ calcd. for : C, 78.22; H, 7.29%); ν_{max} (film) 3440, 3075, 2980, 2945, 2890, 1100 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.55 (6H, d, J 7.1 Hz), 7.14 (9H, m), 4.64 (1H, dd, J 5.7, 12.7 Hz), 3.44 (1H, m), 3.33 (1H, m), 2.78 (1H, d, J 7.1 Hz), 1.98 (2H, m), 0.19 (9H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 143.8, 128.6, 127.9, 127.0, 106.1, 89.3, 87.2, 61.6, 61.0, 37.4, -0.1 ; m/z (M^+) calcd. 414.2015, obsd. 414.2015; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +6.0$ (*c* 1.0, CHCl_3) (61% ee).

(3R)-3-(tert-Butyldimethylsiloxy)-1-(trimethylsilyl)pent-1-yn-5-ol (10): To propargylic alcohol **9** (0.83 g, 2.00 mmol) in DMF (10 ml) was added imidazole (477 mg, 7.01 mmol) and 15 min later *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl chloride (905 mg, 6.00 mmol). After being stirred for 4 h, the reaction mixture was poured into water (10 ml), extracted with 50% ether/hexane (5×10 ml), dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (2.5–5% ether/hexane) to provide 0.94 g (89%) of the silyl ether as a crystalline solid, m.p. 99.4 – 100.6° (Found : C, 75.10; H, 8.42. $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_2\text{Si}_2$ calcd. for : C, 74.94; H, 8.39%); ν_{max} (film) 1266, 1110, 1087 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.43 (6H, m), 7.29 (9H, m), 14.63 (1H, t, J 6.6 Hz), 3.21 (1H, m), 3.16 (1H, m), 2.00 (2H, q, J 6.4 Hz), 0.82 (9H, s), 0.14 (9H, s), 0.12 (3H, s), 0.07 (3H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 144.3, 128.7, 127.7, 126.8, 107.6, 88.6, 86.6, 60.7, 60.0, 39.2, 25.8, 18.2, -0.2 , -4.5 , -5.0 ; m/z (M^+) calcd. 285.1719, obsd. 285.1712; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} +14.0$ (*c* 1.01, CHCl_3) (88% ee).

The above material (242 mg, 0.457 mmol) was taken up in CH_2Cl_2 (2 ml) whereupon a mixture of trifluoroacetic acid/trifluoroacetic anhydride, both 1.83 M in CH_2Cl_2 (0.75 ml), was added dropwise. Reaction proceeded rapidly and, upon completion of the addition, the mixture was cooled to 0° , made basic with Et_3N (1 ml), and poured into methanol

(10 ml). After solvent evaporation, the oily residue was chromatographed on silica gel (20% ether/hexane) to give **10** as a clear oil (120 mg, 92%) (Found : C, 58.65; H, 10.56. $C_{14}H_{30}O_2Si_2$ calcd. for : C, 58.68; H, 10.55%); ν_{max} (film) 1100, 1065 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 4.62 (1H, dd, J 5.0, 6.3 Hz), 3.91 (1H, m), 3.78 (1H, m), 2.34 (1H, s), 1.95 (2H, m), 0.91 (9H, s), 0.16 (12H, s), 0.14 (3H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 106.6, 98.8, 62.7, 60.2, 39.9, 35.7, 18.1, -0.3, -4.5, -5.1; m/z (M^+) calcd. 286.1721, obsd. 286.1753.

(3*R*)-3-(*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy)-5-iodo-1-(trimethylsilyl)pent-1-yne (**11**) : To alkynol **10** (880 mg, 3.07 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (100 ml) at -5° were added triethylamine (1.28 ml, 9.18 mmol) and methanesulfonyl chloride (0.40 ml, 5.2 mmol) dropwise. After 20 min, the reaction mixture was poured into saturated $NaHCO_3$ solution (50 ml) and extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (6×10 ml). The combined organic phases was dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel (25% ether/hexane) to give mesylate as a clear oil (1.022 g, 91%) (Found : C, 49.69; H, 8.84. $C_{15}H_{32}O_4SSi_2$ calcd. for : C, 49.41; H, 8.85%); ν_{max} (film) 1370, 1260, 1190, 1107, 1013 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 4.52 (1H, t, J 6.4 Hz), 4.36 (2H, t, J 6.2 Hz), 3.00 (3H, s), 2.08 (2H, q, J 6.3 Hz), 0.89 (9H, s), 0.15 (12H, s), 0.11 (3H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 105.8, 89.9, 66.4, 59.5, 37.7, 37.2, 25.7, 18.1, -0.3, -4.5, -5.1; m/z (M^+) calcd. 349.1291, obsd. 349.1308.

To the above mesylate (969 mg, 2.66 mmol) in acetone (50 ml) were added $NaHCO_3$ (0.5 g) and NaI (1.34 g, 8.94 mmol). The flask was equipped with a reflux condenser and a drying tube, and the mixture was refluxed overnight, concentrated to leave a yellow-orange solid, diluted with ether (50 ml), and filtered. The filter cake was washed with ether (100 ml). The combined organic phases was concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel (10% ether/hexane) to give **11** as a clear oil (1.038 g, 96%) (Found : C, 42.55; H, 7.36. $C_{14}H_{29}IOSi_2$ calcd. for : C, 42.41; H, 7.37%); ν_{max} (film) 1470, 1370, 1350, 1260, 1180, 1155 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 4.46 (1H, dd, J 7.1, 5.5 Hz), 3.26 (2H, m), 2.15 (2H, m), 0.91 (9H, s), 0.16 (9H, s), 0.15 (6H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 106.2, 89.6, 63.2, 41.8, 25.8, 18.2, 1.6, -0.2, -4.4, -4.9; m/z (M^+) calcd. 369.0767, obsd. 396.0784; $[\alpha]_D^{25} +36.5$ (c 1.01, $CHCl_3$) (88% ee).

(3*R*)-3-(*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy)-1-(trimethylsilyl)pent-1-yn-5-ol (**10**) : To (+)-*B*-methoxy(diisopinocampheyl)borane (17.16 g, 54.2 mmol) in ether (250 ml) at -78° was added allylmagnesium bromide (54.05 ml, 1.0 *M* in ether) via syringe. Then the mixture was allowed to warm

to rt and stirred for 30 min, during which time a white precipitate formed. The mixture was recooled to -78° and **12** (4.686 g, 37.1 mmol) in ether (50 ml) was introduced via cannula and stirred for 4 h prior to the slow addition of 3 *N* NaOH (60 ml) and 30% H_2O_2 (34 ml) (exothermic). The mixture was extracted with ether (6×100 ml). The combined organic layers was dried over K_2CO_3 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (10% ether/hexane) to give **13** as a clear oil (5.24 g, 84%).

To a solution of **13** (5.25 g, 31.1 mmol) in DMF (38 ml) was added imidazole (10.61 g, 155.8 mmol) and after 15 min *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl chloride (14.17 g, 94.0 mmol) in one portion. After 6 h, ether was added (200 ml) and the mixture was washed with water (7×50 ml), saturated NH_4Cl solution (1×100 ml), and brine (5×50 ml). The organic layer was dried over K_2CO_3 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (2.5% ether/hexane) to give **14** as a clear oil (7.77 g, 88%).

Through a solution of **14** (3.89 g, 13.8 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (150 ml) cooled to -78° was bubbled ozone for 16 min with frequent checking for completion by thin layer chromatography. Oxygen was bubbled through to purge the excess ozone. The cold mixture was treated with Ph_3P (2.4 g) and allowed to warm to rt. After 1 d, H_2O_2 (30%; 20 ml) was added and the mixture was extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (6×30 ml). The combined organic phases was dried over K_2CO_3 , concentrated, and used without further purification; 1H nmr (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 9.78 (1H, t, J 2.2 Hz), 4.83 (1H, dd, J 6.8, 4.7 Hz), 2.74 (1H, ddd, J 11.8, 7.1, 2.3 Hz), 2.62 (1H, ddd, J 11.8, 4.7, 2.0 Hz), 0.86 (9H, s), 0.14 (12H, s), 0.11 (3H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 200.3, 105.4, 90.5, 58.6, 51.2, 25.6, 18.0, -0.4, -4.6, -5.1.

A solution of the above material in ethanol (100 ml) was treated with $NaBH_4$ (0.47 g, 12 mmol) in one portion and stirred. After 20 min, 1 *M* HCl was introduced until the solution was acidic (*ca.* 5 ml), and the mixture was extracted with ether (6×15 ml) and dried over K_2CO_3 . The combined organic layer was concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel (10% ether/hexanes) to give **10** as a clear oil (1.77 g, 41% over two steps). This material exhibited spectral properties identical to the material generated earlier.

(2*S*, 3*R*)-4-(*p*-Methoxybenzyloxy)-2,3-epoxy-1-butanol (**16**)^{11,12} : A flame-dried, three-necked flask was charged with CH_2Cl_2 (1 L), 3A molecular sieves (80 g), (+)-diethyl tartrate (7.44 g, 36.1 mmol) and, after cooling to -25° , titanium isopropoxide (8.53 ml, 28.6 mmol). Following 35 min of stirring, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (75 ml, 4 *M* in CH_2Cl_2 , 300 mmol)¹⁶ (dried overnight over 6 g of 4A molecular sieves) was added and allowed to stir for 30 min. The vig-

ously stirred mixture was treated with **15** (29.85 g, 143 mmol) via cannula and allowed to stand at -25° for 8 d prior to being filtered, concentrated, and purified by chromatography on silica gel (50% ethyl acetate/hexane) to give **16** as a clear oil (9.31 g, 29%) along with the starting material (15.64 g, 52%); ^1H nmr (200 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.27–7.24 (2H, m), 6.90–6.86 (2H, m), 4.54 (1H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 4.46 (1H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 3.90–3.84 (1H, m), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.72–3.67 (3H, m), 3.60 (1H, dd, J 7.3, 3.3 Hz), 3.30–3.18 (2H, m); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.4, 129.5, 129.4, 113.9, 73.1, 67.7, 60.7, 55.6, 55.2, 54.6; >56% ee (extrapolated from the literature values of % ee and rotation); $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25}$ 15.8 (c 1.11, CHCl_3) (lit. for the enantiomer of **17**, >98% ee, $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{20}$ -27.4 (c 0.78, CHCl_3))¹².

(2*S*,3*S*)-4-(*p*-Methoxybenzyloxy)-2,3-epoxybutanal (**17**): Oxalyl chloride (6.36 ml, 72.9 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (250 ml) was cooled to -78° whereupon DMSO (10.35 ml, 146 mmol) was added dropwise and stirred for 15 min. Epoxy alcohol **16** (10.90 g, 48.6 mmol) dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 (20 ml) was added to it dropwise and stirred for an additional 30 min whereupon Et_3N (40 ml, 290 mmol) was introduced. The reaction mixture was allowed to warm to rt prior to being washed with water (2 \times 50 ml) and saturated NH_4Cl solution (3 \times 50 ml). The aqueous washings were extracted with CH_2Cl_2 (5 \times 30 ml) and the combined organic phases was dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (30% ether/hexane) to give **17** as a pungent oil (4.82 g, 45%); ν_{max} (film) 1725, 1590, 1515, 1465, 1450, 1425, 1365, 1304, 1250, 1175 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 9.41 (1H, d, J 4.8 Hz), 7.24–7.20 (2H, m), 6.90–6.85 (2H, m), 4.50 (1H, d, J 12.2 Hz), 4.46 (1H, d, J 12.2 Hz), 3.82–3.77 (1H, m), 3.79 (3H, s), 3.72 (1H, dd, J 11.8, 4.6 Hz), 3.48 (1H, dd, J 8.0, 4.6 Hz), 3.39 (1H, dd, J 4.8, 4.8 Hz); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 197.6, 159.4, 129.4, 129.1, 113.8, 73.1, 65.8, 57.9, 57.2, 55.1; m/z (M^+) calcd. 222.0892, obsd. 222.0897.

(3*R*,6*R*,7*R*,8*S*)-3-(*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy)-7,8-epoxy-9-(*p*-methoxybenzyloxy)-1-(trimethylsilyl)non-1-yn-6-ol (**18**): A solution of **11** (11.60 g, 29.2 mmol) in dry ether (250 ml) at -78° was treated with *tert*-butyllithium (38.0 ml, 1.7 *M* in hexanes, 65 mmol) and, after 15 min, allowed to warm to rt and stirred for 30 min. After recooling to -78° , a solution of **17** (3.64 g, 16.4 mmol) in ether (10 ml) also at -78° was added via cannula and allowed to warm to rt over 1 h. The reaction mixture was poured into water (100 ml) prior to being extracted with ether (6 \times 20 ml), dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (20% ether/hexanes) to give 5.82 g (72%) of diastereomerically pure **18** as a clear oil (5.82 g, 72%) (Found : C, 63.21; H, 8.95. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{44}\text{O}_5\text{Si}_2$ calcd. for : C,

63.37; H, 9.00%); ν_{max} (film) 3440, 1515, 1470, 1258, 1180 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.29 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 6.87 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 4.97 (1H, td, J 8.0, 2.7 Hz), 4.58 (1H, d, J 11.5 Hz), 4.51 (1H, d, J 11.5 Hz), 4.60–4.40 (1H, m), 3.96 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz), 3.92 (1H, d, J 3.0 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.54 (1H, dd, J 11.7, 7.2 Hz), 3.20 (1H, ddd, J 7.2, 4.2, 3.0 Hz), 3.06 (1H, dd, J 8.5, 4.2 Hz), 2.52 (1H, dddd, J 17.2, 14.0, 10.6, 2.5 Hz), 2.37 (1H, m), 2.22 (1H, dddd, J 12.5, 10.0, 7.7, 2.4 Hz), 1.90 (1H, ddd, J 18.0, 9.8, 8.1 Hz), 0.91 (9H, s), 0.14 (9H, s), 0.12 (3H, s), 0.10 (3H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.2, 152.7, 134.7, 130.0, 129.4, 113.7, 73.5, 72.7, 71.1, 68.0, 60.4, 56.3, 55.2, 29.1, 25.6, 25.2, 17.8, -0.8 , -4.1 , -5.3 ; m/z (M^+) calcd. 492.2727, obsd. 492.2696.

(3*R*,7*R*,8*S*)-3-(*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy)-7,8-epoxy-9-(*p*-methoxybenzyloxy)-1-(trimethylsilyl)non-1-yn-6-one (**19**): To a solution of **18** (0.24 g, 0.49 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (70 ml) at rt was added the Dess-Martin periodinane (1.03 g, 2.43 mmol) in three portions. The reaction mixture was stirred open to air for 30 min prior to addition of 60% ether/hexane (100 ml), filtration through a plug of silica, concentration of the filtrate, and purification of the residue by chromatography on silica gel (15% ether/hexanes) to give **19** as a clear oil (0.22 g, 92%) (Found : C, 63.73; H, 8.72. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{42}\text{O}_5\text{Si}_2$ calcd. for : C, 63.63; H, 8.63%); ν_{max} (film) 1678, 1250, 1146, 1030 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.24 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz), 6.85 (2H, d, J 8.6 Hz), 5.00 (1H, td, J 8.1, 2.9 Hz), 4.48 (1H, d, J 11.2 Hz), 4.40 (1H, d, J 11.2 Hz), 3.87 (1H, d, J 4.6 Hz), 3.79 (3H, s), 3.61 (1H, dd, J 11.0, 5.6 Hz), 3.51 (1H, dd, J 11.0, 4.8 Hz), 3.38 (1H, dd, J 10.2, 4.9 Hz), 2.62–2.40 (2H, m), 2.28 (1H, ddd, J 11.9, 8.9, 3.5 Hz), 1.92 (1H, ddd, J 17.7, 10.0, 7.7 Hz), 0.86 (9H, s), 0.12 (9H, s), 0.06 (3H, s), 0.04 (3H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 201.0, 166.3, 159.2, 134.9, 129.9, 129.5, 113.7, 73.6, 73.0, 66.5, 57.2, 56.9, 55.2, 29.2, 26.0, 25.7, 17.8, -0.4 , -4.6 , -5.1 ; m/z (M^+) calcd. 490.2571, obsd. 490.2578.

(3*R*,7*R*,8*S*)-3-(*tert*-Butyldimethylsiloxy)-7,8-epoxy-9-(*p*-methoxybenzyloxy)-6-methylene-1-(trimethylsilyl)non-1-yne (**20**): To methyltriphenylphosphonium bromide (0.11 g, 0.31 mmol) in THF (1 ml) at rt was added potassium hexamethyldisilazide (0.58 ml, 0.5 *M* in toluene, 0.29 mmol) dropwise via syringe and, after 20 min, a solution of **19** (73.3 mg, 0.149 mmol) in THF (1 ml) via cannula. After stirring for 15 min, the reaction mixture was poured into saturated NH_4Cl solution prior to being extracted with ether (7 \times 2 ml), dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (5% ether/hexanes) to give **20** as a clear oil (21.1 mg, 29%) and along with the starting material (21.1 mg, 29%); ν_{max} (film) 1613, 1514, 1471,

1249, 1173, 1145 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.30–7.24 (2H, m), 6.89–6.84 (2H, m), 5.01 (1H, t, J 12.5 Hz), 4.86–4.80 (2H, m), 4.54 (1H, d, J 11.4 Hz), 4.45 (1H, d, J 11.4 Hz), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.65 (1H, dd, J 11.1, 4.0 Hz), 3.58 (1H, dd, J 4.4, 0.9 Hz), 3.45 (1H, dd, J 11.0, 6.6 Hz), 3.31–3.24 (12H, m), 2.64–2.53 (1H, m), 2.36 (1H, ddd, J 18.2, 14.0, 9.2 Hz), 2.25–2.16 (1H, m), 1.95–1.85 (1H, m), 0.86 (9H, s), 0.08 (9H, s), 0.03 (6H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.2, 156.3, 141.2, 130.2, 129.4, 129.4, 113.7, 112.5, 73.3, 72.8, 67.4, 57.5, 57.1, 55.3, 29.5, 26.3, 25.8, 18.0, 0.0, –4.7, –5.1; m/z (M^+) calcd. 488.2728, obsd. 488.2753.

(3R,7S,8S)-7,8-Epoxy-9-(p-methoxybenzyloxy)-6-methylene-1-(trimethylsilyl)non-1-yn-3-ol (**6**): To a solution of **20** (21.8 mg, 0.045 mmol) in THF (2 ml) at 0° was added TBAF (0.045 ml), 1.0 M in THF, 0.045 mmol). After being stirred for 7 h, the reaction mixture was poured into saturated NaHCO_3 solution (1 ml) prior to being extracted with ether (6 \times 1 ml), dried over Na_2SO_4 , concentrated, and chromatographed on silica gel (15% ether/hexane) to give 11.3 mg (68%) of **6** as a clear oil (11.3 g, 68%); ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.29–7.24 (2H, m), 6.90–6.86 (2H, m), 4.97 (1H, t, J 1.7 Hz), 4.87 (1H, d, J 1.9 Hz), 4.80–4.70 (1H, m), 4.50 (1H, s), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.61 (2H, d, J 5.8 Hz), 3.48 (1H, dd, J 4.2, 0.9 Hz), 3.40–3.30 (2H, m), 3.32 (1H, dd, J 5.7, 4.3 Hz), 2.78–2.66 (1H, m), 2.45 (1H, dd, J 17.2, 9.1 Hz), 2.33–2.24 (1H, m), 1.82 (1H, dddd, J 17.2, 11.2, 7.9, 5.9 Hz), 0.12 (9H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 159.4, 157.5, 141.9, 134.2, 129.7, 129.4, 113.8, 112.5, 73.2, 72.2, 65.6, 57.2, 55.3, 28.2, 27.1, –0.4 (one C not observed).

(1R,5S,1'S)-5-(1'-Hydroxy-2-(p-methoxybenzyloxy)ethyl)-4-methylene-1-(trimethylsilylacetylene)pyran (**5**): To a solution of **6** (11.5 mg, 0.031 mmol) in CH_2Cl_2 (0.5 ml) at -15° was added camphorsulfonic acid (ca. 10 mg) and, after 4 h, triethylamine (0.25 ml). The reaction mixture was concentrated and chromatographed on silica gel (20% ether/hexane) to give **5** as clear oil (8.5 mg, 74%); ^1H nmr (300 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 7.28–7.25 (2H, m), 6.89–6.85 (2H, m), 5.06 (1H, s), 4.84 (1H, s), 4.68 (1H, t, J 7.8 Hz), 4.52 (1H, d, J 11.5 Hz), 3.47 (1H, d, J 11.5 Hz), 3.34 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.04–3.97 (1H, m), 3.80 (3H, s), 3.64 (1H, dd, J

10.1, 2.9 Hz), 3.48 (1H, dd, J 10.1 5.4 Hz), 2.70–2.65 (3H, m), 2.33–2.21 (1H, m), 1.91 (1H, ddd, J 17.0, 9.5, 7.6 Hz), 0.19 (9H, s); ^{13}C nmr (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 167.0, 155.9, 141.2, 131.0, 129.5, 128.8, 114.1, 112.0, 78.5, 71.9; 71.7, 71.1, 54.7, 30.2, 28.5, 0.7 (one C not observed); m/z (M^+) calcd. 374.1829, obsd. 374.1871.

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